

1-(2-Quinolylazo)-2-acenaphthyleneol (QAAc) as a Selective and Sensitive Chromogenic Reagent for Microdetermination of Palladium (II)

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Palladium forms two coloured complexes, viz., green and red, with 1-(2-quinolylazo)-2-acenaphthyleneol, at low and high pH's respectively. The green (1:1) complex has an absorbance maximum at 670 nm with the sensitivity of 0.0075 $\mu\text{g cm}^2$. The red (1:2) complex exhibits maximum absorbance at 550 nm and the sensitivity of the colour reaction is 0.0049 $\mu\text{g/cm}^2$. The reagent has been employed for microdetermination of palladium in synthetic solutions containing other metals present in alloys.

VARIOUS chromogenic reagents used for micro-determination of palladium have been reviewed by various workers^{1,2}. Among the various heterocyclic azo dyes; PAN³, PAR³ and TAR⁴ have been satisfactorily used for spectrophotometric determination of palladium(II). In the present communication, the sensitive reaction of another heterocyclic azo dye, 1-(2-quinolylazo)-2-acenaphthyleneol (QAAc), with palladium has been explored extensively for the micro determination of palladium, both at low and high pH levels, in presence of various foreign ions. The method has been found to be fairly selective.

Experimental

Reagents. Stock solution of palladium(II) was prepared by dissolving appropriate amount of palladium chloride (Johnson and Matthey, London), in 2N hydrochloric acid. The solution was standardised gravimetrically with dimethylglyoxime.

QAAc was synthesised⁵ and its stock solution was obtained by dissolving the requisite quantity in pure methanol. In no case reagent solutions older than a week were used.

Sodium acetate, hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide (reagent quality) were used for pH adjustments. Acetate or KCl/HCl buffers were employed.

Apparatus: A Unicam spectrophotometer, SP-600, with 10 mm matched glass cell was used for absorbance measurements.

A Metrohm pH meter, type E-350, with saturated calomel and glass electrode assembly was used for pH measurements.

Results and Discussion

Addition of the reagent (QAAc) solution to palladium(II) solution resulted in an instant colour.

However, 5-10 mins, warming was necessary for the attainment of maximum colour. The complexes of QAAc with palladium were found to be insoluble in aqueous solution, but soluble in 75% v/v (methanol : water) mixture. The complexes were extractable in many water immiscible organic solvents. However, chloroform was used for the purpose, as the absorbance was maximum and remained constant for at least five to six hrs.

Spectral Characteristics

Series of solutions containing palladium(II) ($4 \times 10^{-5} M$) and QAAc ($6 \times 10^{-4} M$) at different pH

Fig. 1. Absorption Spectra of the Pd-QAAc complexes at Different pH.

Conc. of Pd²⁺ Soln. $4 \times 10^{-5} M$

Conc. of QAAc Soln. $6 \times 10^{-4} M$

Curve I at pH	
II	2.7
III	4.0
IV	6.0
V	8.0
VI	10.0
VII	11.4

values, were warmed for 5 min. on a steam bath and after extracting them into chloroform, their spectra were recorded against the reagent blanks prepared under identical conditions. It has been found (Fig. 1) that two peaks, one at 670 nm and the other at 550 nm, were obtained at low and high pH respectively. The colour of the complex formed at low pH (λ_{max} at 670 nm) is green and that formed at high pH (λ_{max} at 550 nm) is red, indicating the formation of two different complexes in the system.

Physico-chemical Characteristics of the Complexes

The physico-chemical characteristics of the complexes have been summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF Pd-QAAc COMPLEXES

Characteristics	Green Complex	Red Complex
1. λ_{max}	670 nm	550 nm
2. Workable pH range	2.2—3.0	8.0—10.6
3. Moles of QAAc needed for complexation per mole of metal	2	4
4. Composition of Complex (M : L)	1 : 1	1 : 2
5. Validity of Beer's Law (in ppm)	3.2—10.65	0—7.15
6. Optimum range for accurate determination of metal (in ppm)	3.5—7.4	1.1—5.0
7. Molar extinction (ϵ) Coefficient	1.42×10^4	2.13×10^4
8. Sandell's Sensitivity ($\mu\text{g Pd/cm}^2$)	0.0075	0.0049

Recommended Procedure

To a suitable aliquot containing 35 to 70 μg (for green complex) or 12 to 50 μg (for red complex) of palladium(II), add sufficient excess (3 ml of $10^{-3}M$) of QAAc solution, followed by 4 ml of the buffer of requisite pH (Table 1). Raise the volume of aqueous phase to 10 ml, keeping 50% v/v methanol concentration. Heat the contents in 50 ml pyrex bottle on a steam bath for 5–10 min. Extract the palladium-QAAc complex in 10 ml of freshly distilled chloroform. Measure the absorbance of the complex vs. reagent blank under identical conditions at the corresponding λ_{max} and deduce the amount of palladium from the calibration curve drawn under similar conditions.

Study of the Effect of Diverse ions

The effect of diverse ions was studied by taking requisite amount of palladium (4.24 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for green complex or 3.39 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for red complex) and adding different amounts of diverse ions. The tolerance limits for the diverse ions which did not cause deviation of more than $\pm 2\%$ in absorbance are given in

parentheses below :

Green Complex

The ions I^- , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$, CNS^- , CN^- , thiourea and EDTA interfere seriously.

NO_2^- , NO_3^- , Ac^- , BO_3^{3-} , PO_4^{3-} (400); Ox^{2-} , citrate, tartrate, SO_4^{2-} (100); F^- , Br^- (50).

Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , V^{5+} , Pb^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} , Tl^+ , Cr^{3+} (1000); Hg^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , and Fe^{3+} , Mn^{2+} , In^{3+} (250); Ag^+ , Au^{3+} , Ti^{4+} , Pt^{4+} (100); Cu^{2+} (20); Ru^{3+} , Rh^{3+} , Ir^{3+} (5); Os^{8+} (2).

Red Complex

The ions CN^- , I^- , NO_2^- , CNS^- , thiourea, $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ and F^- interfere seriously.

Br^- , NO_2^- , tartrate (1000); PO_4^{3-} (500); citrate (200); EDTA (150).

Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} (40); (Masked with EDTA); Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Hg^{2+} (25); (Masked with EDTA); Ti^+ , V^{5+} , W^{6+} , Mo^{6+} , Ag^+ , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} , Ge^{4+} , Al^{3+} (20); Au^{3+} (10); Os^{8+} , Ru^{3+} (5).

Attempts to mask Ir and Fe were unsuccessful.

Determination of Palladium in Alloys

To ascertain the selectivity of the reagent at low pH, the method was successfully used for determination of palladium in alloys. Synthetic solutions, similar in composition to that of alloys of palladium

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF PALLADIUM IN SYNTHETIC SOLUTIONS CONTAINING OTHER METALS PRESENT IN ALLOYS

S.No.	Amount of Pd	Amount of other metals present	Amount of Pd found	% error
1.	6.0 ppm	4.0 ppm of Cu^{2+}	6.03	+0.5
2.	6.0 "	4.0 ppm of Cu^{2+}	6.02	+0.33
3.	6.0 "	4.0 ppm of Ag^+	6.01	+0.16
4.	6.0 "	4.0 ppm of Ag^+	5.98	-0.33
5.	6.0 "	6.0 ppm of Au^{3+}	6.00	0.0
6.	6.0 "	6.0 ppm of Au^{3+}	6.00	0.0

were prepared and the amount of palladium was determined following the recommended procedure at low pH. The errors in the results obtained, recorded in Table 2 are within $\pm 1.0\%$.

Discussion

Although various heterocyclic azo dyes such as PAN, PAR and TAR have proved to be sensitive reagents for the micro determination of palladium, some of the associated metals like copper, silver, gold and cobalt interfere in these methods. In the present study, the interferences of most of the associated metals were found to be negligible even when they were present in four to five times molar excess. The reagent has also been used successfully for the determination of palladium in alloys. As regards the sensitivity of the reagent (0.0075/670 nm, 0.0049/550 nm), it is comparable with the sensitivities

of other heterocyclic azo dyes, viz., PAR³ (0.0057/440 nm, 0.012/630 nm), TAR⁴ (0.013/650 nm), PAN⁶ (0.016/610 nm, 0.013/665 nm).

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